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RAMANUJAN'S SPT-CRANK FOR MARKED OVERPARTITIONS

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ABSTRACT

In 1916, Ramanujan's showed the spt-crank for marked overpartitions. The corresponding special functions $\overline{S}(z, x)$, $\overline{S}_1(z, x)$ and $\overline{S}_2(z, x)$ are found in Ramanujan's notebooks, part 111.

In 2009, Bingmann, Lovejoy and Osburn defined the generating functions for $\overline{spt}(n)$, $\overline{spt}_1(n)$ and $\overline{spt}_2(n)$. In 2012, Andrews, Garvan, and Liang defined the $\overline{sptcrank}$ in terms of partition pairs. In this article the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined, not overlined and odd, not overlined and even are discussed, and the vector partitions and $\overline{S}$ -partitions with 4 components, each a partition with certain restrictions are also discussed. The generating functions $\overline{spt}(n)$, $\overline{spt}_1(n)$, $\overline{spt}_2(n)$, $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$ are shown with the corresponding results in terms of modulo 3, where the generating functions $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$ are collected from Ramanujan's notebooks, part 111. This paper shows how to prove the Theorem 1 in terms of $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$, Theorem 2 in terms of $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, n)$ and Theorem 3 in terms of $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$ respectively with the numerical examples, and shows how to prove the Theorems 4,5 and 6 with the help of $\overline{sptcrank}$ in terms of partition pairs. In 2014, Garvan and Jennings-Shaffer are able to defined the $\overline{sptcrank}$ for marked overpartitions. This paper also shows another results with the help of 6 $\overline{SP}$ -partition pairs of 3, help of 20 $\overline{SP}_1$ -partition pairs of 5 and help of 15 $\overline{SP}_2$ -partition pairs of 8 respectively.

Keywords:

Components, congruent, crank, overpartitions, overlined, weight.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we give some related definitions of $\overline{spt}(n)$, $\overline{spt}_1(n)$, $\overline{spt}_2(n)$, various product notations, vector partitions and $\overline{S}$ - partitions, $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}}(m, t, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, t, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, t, n)$, $\overline{S}(z, x)$, $\overline{S}_1(z, x)$, $\overline{S}_2(z, x)$, marked partition and $\overline{sptcrank}$ for marked overpartitions. We discuss the generating functions for $\overline{spt}(n)$, $\overline{spt}_1(n)$, $\overline{spt}_2(n)$ and prove the Corollaries 1, 2 and 3 with the help of generating functions for $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$, $M_{\overline{S}_1}(m, n)$ and $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$ respectively. We prove the Results 1, 2 and 3 with the help of 8 vector partitions from $\overline{S}$ of 3, from $\overline{S}_1$ of 3 and of 3 vector partitions from $\overline{S}_2$ of 4 respectively. We prove the Theorems 1, 2 and 3 with the help of various generating functions and establish the Corollaries 4, 5 and 6 with the help special series $\overline{S}(z, x)$, $\overline{S}_1(z, x)$ and $\overline{S}_2(z, x)$ respectively, where the special series $\overline{S}(z, x)$, $\overline{S}_1(z, x)$ and $\overline{S}_2(z, x)$ are collected from **Ramanujan’s notebooks, part 111**, and prove the Theorems 4, 5 and 6 with the help of $\overline{sptcrank}$ in terms of partition pairs (λ_1, λ_2) when $0 < s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2)$. We establish the Results 4, 5 and 6 using the $\overline{crank}$ of partition pairs $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$ and analyze the Corollaries 7,8, and 9 with the help of 42 marked overpartitions of 6, 36 marked overpartitions of 6, 260 marked overpartitions of 10 respectively.

2. SOME RELATED DEFINITIONS

$\overline{spt}(n)$: The number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined is denoted by $\overline{spt}(n)$ for example; $\overline{spt}(1) = 1, \overline{spt}(2) = 3, \overline{spt}(3) = 6, \overline{spt}(4) = 13 \dots$

$\overline{spt}_1(n)$: The number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined and odd is denoted by $\overline{spt}_1(n)$, for example; $\overline{spt}_1(1) = 1, \overline{spt}_1(2) = 2, \overline{spt}_1(3) = 6, \overline{spt}_1(4) = 10 \dots$

$\overline{spt}_2(n)$: The number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined and even is denoted by $\overline{spt}_2(n)$ for example; $\overline{spt}_2(1) = 0, \overline{spt}_2(2) = 1, \overline{spt}_2(3) = 0, \overline{spt}_2(4) = 3 \dots$

Product Notations:

$$(x)_\infty = (1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots$$

$$(x^2; x^2)_\infty = (1-x^2)(1-x^4)\dots$$

$$(x)_k = (1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots(1-x^k)$$

$$(-x^5; x)_\infty = (1+x^5)(1+x^6)(1+x^7)\dots$$

Where $|x| < 1$.

Vector Partitions and $\overline{S}$ - partitions [5]:

A vector partition can be done with 4 components each partition with certain restrictions.

Let $\vec{V} = D \times P \times P \times D$ where D denotes the set of all partitions into distinct parts, P denotes the set of all partitions. For a partition π , we let $s(\pi)$ denote the smallest part of π (with the convention that the empty partition has smallest part ∞), $\#(\pi)$ the number of parts in π , and $|\pi|$ the sum of the parts of π .

For $\vec{\pi} = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \pi_3, \pi_4) \in \vec{V}$, we define the weight $\omega(\vec{\pi}) = (-1)^{\#(\pi_1)-1}$, the crank

$$c(\vec{\pi}) = \#(\pi_2) - \#(\pi_3), \text{ the norm } \left| \vec{\pi} \right| = |\pi_1| + |\pi_2| + |\pi_3| + |\pi_4|.$$

We say $\vec{\pi}$ is a vector partition of n if $|\vec{\pi}| = n$. Let $\bar{S}$ denote the subset of $\vec{V}$ and it is given by

$$\bar{S} = \left\{ (\pi_1, \pi_2, \pi_3, \pi_4) \in \vec{V}, 1 \leq s(\pi_1) < \infty, s(\pi_1) \leq s(\pi_2), s(\pi_1) \leq s(\pi_3), s(\pi_1) < s(\pi_4) \right\}.$$

$M_{\bar{S}}(m, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}}(m, n)$.

$M_{\bar{S}}(m, t, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}$ with crank congruent to m modulo t counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}}(m, t, n)$.

Let $\bar{S}_1$ denote the subset of $\bar{S}$ with $s(\pi_1)$ odd.

$M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}_1$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n)$.

$M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, t, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}_1$ with crank congruent to m modulo t counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, t, n)$.

Let $\bar{S}_2$ denotes the subset of $\bar{S}$ with $s(\pi_1)$ even.

$M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}_2$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n)$.

$M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, t, n)$: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}_2$ with crank congruent to m modulo t counted according to the weight ω is exactly $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, t, n)$.

$\bar{S}(z, x)$: The series $\bar{S}(z, x)$ is defined by the generating function for $M_{\bar{S}}(m, n)$

$$\text{i.e., } \bar{S}(z, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}}(m, n).$$

$\bar{S}_1(z, x)$: The series $\bar{S}_1(z, x)$ is defined by the generating function for $M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n)$;

$$\bar{S}_1(z, x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n) z^m x^n.$$

$\bar{S}_2(z, x)$: The series $\bar{S}_2(z, x)$ is defined by the generating function for $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n)$

$$\text{i.e., } \bar{S}_2(z, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n) z^m x^n.$$

Marked Partition [1]: We define a marked partition as a pair (λ, k) where λ is a partition and k is an integer identifying one of its smallest parts i.e. $k = 1, 2, \dots, v(\lambda)$, where $v(\lambda)$ is the number of smallest parts of λ .

sptcrank for Marked overpartitions[6]: We define a marked overpartitions of n as a pair (π, j) where π is an overpartition of n in which the smallest parts is not overlined and j is an integer $1 \leq j \leq v(\pi)$, where $v(\pi)$ is the number of smallest parts to π . It is clear that $\overline{\text{spt}}(n) = \#$ of marked overpartitions (π, j) of n . For example; there are 3 marked overpartitions of 2

Like- $(2, 1), (1+1, 1), (1+1, 2)$ so that $\overline{\text{spt}}(2) = 3$.

Again there are 6 marked overpartitions of 3 like- $(3, 1), (2+1, 1), (\bar{2}+1, 1), (1+1+1, 1), (1+1+1, 2)$ and $(1+1+1, 3)$ so that $\overline{\text{spt}}(3) = 6$.

3. THE GENERATING FUNCTION FOR $\overline{\text{spt}}(n)$

$\overline{\text{spt}}(n)$ is the number of smallest parts in the overpartitons of n with smallest part not overlined like-
Table-1

N	The type of smallest parts in the overpartitons of n	$\overline{\text{spt}}(n)$
1	$\dot{1}$	1
2	$\dot{2}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}$	3
3	$\dot{3}, 2+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+\dot{1}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}$	6
4	$\dot{4}, 3+\dot{1}, \bar{3}+1, \dot{2}+\dot{2}, 2+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}$	13
...	...	...

We make the expression

$$\begin{aligned} & \overline{\text{spt}}(1)x + \overline{\text{spt}}(2)x^2 + \overline{\text{spt}}(3)x^3 + \overline{\text{spt}}(4)x^4 + \dots \\ &= 1.x + 3.x^2 + 6.x^3 + 13.x^4 + 22.x^5 + 42.x^6 + \dots \\ &= \frac{x(1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^2(1+x^3)(1+x^4)\dots}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \dots \quad [\text{Andrews et al (2013)}] \\ &= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(x^2; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2(x^3; x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n(-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \\ &\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n(-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{\text{spt}}(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

From above we get; $\overline{\text{spt}}(3) = 6, \overline{\text{spt}}(6) = 42, \dots$

i.e. $\overline{\text{spt}}(3.1) = 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \overline{\text{spt}}(3.2) = 42 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \dots$

We can conclude that;

$$\overline{spt}(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \text{ for } n \geq 0.$$

3.1. THE GENERATING FUNCTION FOR $\overline{spt}_1(n)$

$\overline{spt}_1(n)$ is the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined and odd like-

Table-2

n	The type of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n	$\overline{spt}_1(n)$
1	$\dot{1}$	1
2	$\dot{1}+\dot{1}$	2
3	$\dot{3}, 2+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+\dot{1}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}$	6
4	$3+\dot{1}, \bar{3}+\dot{1}, 2+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}$	10
...		...

We make the expression

$$\begin{aligned} & \overline{spt}_1(1)x + \overline{spt}_1(2)x^2 + \overline{spt}_1(3)x^3 + \overline{spt}_1(4)x^4 + \dots \\ &= x^2 + 2x^2 + 6x^3 + 10x^4 + 20x^5 + 36x^6 + \dots \\ &= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_\infty}{(1-x)^2(x^2; x)_\infty} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_\infty}{(1-x^3)^2(x^4; x)_\infty} + \frac{x^5(-x^6; x)_\infty}{(1-x^5)^2(x^6; x)_\infty} + \dots \text{ [Lovejoy et al (2009)]} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}(-x^{2n+2}; x)_\infty}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2(x^{2n+2}; x)_\infty} \\ &\therefore \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}(-x^{2n+2}; x)_\infty}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2(x^{2n+2}; x)_\infty} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_1(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

From above we get $\overline{spt}_1(3) = 6, \overline{spt}_1(6) = 36, \dots$

i.e., $\overline{spt}_1(3.1) = 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \overline{spt}_1(3.2) = 36 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \dots$

We can conclude that

$$\overline{spt}_1(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \text{ for } n \geq 0 \text{ [4]}$$

From above we get $\overline{spt}_1(1) = 1, \overline{spt}_1(9) = 165, \dots$

i.e. $\overline{spt}_1(1) = 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \overline{spt}_1(3^2) = 165 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \dots$

We can conclude that

$$\overline{spt}_1(n) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \text{ if } n \text{ is an odd square.}$$

Again we get;

$$\overline{spt}_1(5) = 10, \overline{spt}_1(10) = 260, \dots$$

i.e. $\overline{spt}_1(5.1) = 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \overline{spt}_1(5.2) = 260 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \dots$

We can conclude that;

$$\overline{spt}_1(5n) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}.$$

3.2. THE GENERATING FUNCTION FOR $\overline{spt}_2(n)$:

$\overline{spt}_2(n)$ is the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined and even like-

Table-3

n	The type of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n	$\overline{spt}_2(n)$
1	none	0
2	$\dot{2}$	1
3	none	0
4	$\dot{4}, \dot{2} + \dot{2}$	3
5	$3 + \dot{2}, \overline{3} + \dot{2}$	2
...	...	...

We make the expression

$$\overline{spt}_2(1)x + \overline{spt}_2(2)x^2 + \overline{spt}_2(3)x^3 + \overline{spt}_2(4)x^4 + \overline{spt}_2(5)x^5 + \dots$$

$$= 0.x + 1.x^2 + 0.x^3 + 3.x^4 + 2.x^5 + 6.x^6 + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_\infty}{(1-x^2)^2(x^3; x)_\infty} + \frac{x^4(-x^5; x)_\infty}{(1-x^4)^2(x^5; x)_\infty} + \dots \quad [10]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}(-x^{2n+1}; x)_\infty}{(1-x^{2n})^2(x^{2n+1}; x)_\infty}$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}(-x^{2n+1}; x)_\infty}{(1-x^{2n})^2(x^{2n+1}; x)_\infty} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_2(n)x^n.$$

From above we get $\overline{spt}_2(3) = 0, \overline{spt}_2(6) = 6, \dots$

i.e., $\overline{spt}_2(3.1) = 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \overline{spt}_2(3.2) = 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \dots$

We can conclude that $\overline{spt}_2(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

We also get $\overline{spt}_2(4) = 3, \overline{spt}_2(7) = 6, \dots$

i.e., $\overline{spt}_2(3+1) = 3 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \overline{spt}_2(3.2+1) = 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \dots$

We can conclude that $\overline{spt}_2(3n+1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

Again from above we get; $\overline{spt}_2(3) = 0, \overline{spt}_2(8) = 15, \dots$

i.e., $\overline{spt}_2(3) = 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \overline{spt}_2(5+3) = 15 \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \dots$

We can conclude that $\overline{spt}_2(5n+3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. [5]

Corollary 1: $\overline{spt}(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\overline{s}}(m, n)$

Proof: The generating function for $M_{\overline{s}}(m, n)$ [3] is given by;

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\overline{s}}(m, n) z^m x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{n+1}; x)_\infty (-x^{n+1}; x)_\infty}{(zx^n; x)_\infty (z^{-1}x^n; x)_\infty}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{If } z = 1, \text{ then we get; } & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}}(m, n) x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^n; x)_{\infty} (x^n; x)_{\infty}} \\
 & = \frac{x(x^2; x)_{\infty} (-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(x; x)_{\infty}^2} + \frac{x^2(x^3; x)_{\infty} (-x^4; x)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}^2} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty} (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2\dots} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty} (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)^2\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(x^2; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2(x^3; x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\
 & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^n)^2 (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n) x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{i.e; } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n) x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}}(m, n) x^n.$$

Now equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$\overline{spt}(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}}(m, n). \text{ Hence The Corollary.}$$

$$\text{Corollary 2: } \overline{spt}_1(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n)$$

$$\text{Proof: we get } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n) z^m x^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}.$$

$$\text{If } z = 1, \text{ then we get; } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n) x^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty} (x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(x; x)_{\infty}^2} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty} (x^4; x)_{\infty}}{(x^3; x)_{\infty}^2} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty} (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)^2\dots} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty} (1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots}{(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)^2\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)\dots} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2 (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_1(n) x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{i.e., } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n) x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt_1(n)} x^n.$$

Now equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get

$$\overline{spt_1(n)} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n). \text{ Hence The Corollary.}$$

Corollary 3: $\overline{spt_2(n)} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n)$

Proof: The generating function for $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n)$ is given by;

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n) z^m x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}.$$

If $z = 1$, then, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n) x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}$

$$= \frac{x^2 (-x^3; x)_{\infty} (x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}^2} + \frac{x^4 (-x^5; x)_{\infty} (x^5; x)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x)_{\infty}^2} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x^2 (-x^3; x)_{\infty} (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x^2)^2 (1-x^3)^2 \dots} + \frac{x^4 (-x^5; x)_{\infty} (1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^4)^2 (1-x^5)^2 \dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x^2 (-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2 (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \frac{x^4 (-x^5; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^4)^2 (1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n})^2 (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt_2(n)} x^n.$$

$$\text{i.e., } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt_2(n)} x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n) x^n.$$

Now equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$\overline{spt_2(n)} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m, n). \text{ Hence The Corollary.}$$

Result 1: $M_{\bar{S}}(0,3,3) = M_{\bar{S}}(1,3,3) = M_{\bar{S}}(2,3,3) = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt}(3).$

Proof: We prove the result with an example. We see the vector partitions from $\bar{S}$ of 3 along with their weights and cranks are given as follows.

Table 4:

$\bar{S}$ -vector partition $(\vec{\pi})$ of 3	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $c(\vec{\pi})$
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$\vec{\pi}_1 = (1, \phi, \phi, 2)$	+ 1	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (1, \phi, 1+1, \phi)$	+1	-2
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (1, 1+1, \phi, \phi)$	+1	2
$\vec{\pi}_4 = (1, 1, 1, \phi)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_5 = (1, \phi, 2, \phi)$	+1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_6 = (1, 2, \phi, \phi)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_7 = (1+2, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	-1	0
$\vec{\pi}_8 = (3, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	+1	0
	$\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 6$	

Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition.

Thus we have, $M_{\bar{5}}(0,3,3) = +1+1-1+1 = 2$, $M_{\bar{5}}(1,3,3) = M_{\bar{5}}(-2,3,3) = 1+1 = 2$,

$$M_{\bar{5}}(2,3,3) = M_{\bar{5}}(-1,3,3) = 1+1 = 2$$

$$\therefore M_{\bar{5}}(0,3,3) = M_{\bar{5}}(1,3,3) = M_{\bar{5}}(2,3,3) = 2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 6 = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt}(3) . \text{ Hence The Result.}$$

Now from above table we get; $\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 6$

$$i.e., \sum_{k=0}^2 M_{\bar{5}}(k,3,3) = 6$$

$$\therefore \overline{spt}(3) = \sum_{k=0}^2 M_{\bar{5}}(k,3,3) = \sum \omega(\vec{\pi}).$$

$$\text{We define } M_{\bar{5}}(k, t, m) = \sum_{m=k(\text{mod } t)} M_{\bar{5}}(m, n)$$

$$\text{and } \overline{spt}(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{5}}(m, n) = \sum_{k=0}^{t-1} M_{\bar{5}}(k, t, n).$$

$$\text{Result 2: } N_{\bar{5}_1}(0,3,3) = N_{\bar{5}_1}(1,3,3) = N_{\bar{5}_1}(2,3,3) = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt}_1(3)$$

Proof: We prove the result with an example. We see the vector partitions from $\bar{S}_1$ of 3 along with their weights and cranks are given as follows:

Table 5:

$\overline{S_1}$ -vector partition $\vec{\pi}$ of 3	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $c(\vec{\pi})$	(mod 3)
$\vec{\pi}_1 = (3, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	+1	0	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (1+2, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	-1	0	0
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (1, 2, \phi, \phi)$	+1	1	1
$\vec{\pi}_4 = (1, \phi, 2, \phi)$	+1	-1	2
$\vec{\pi}_5 = (1, 1, 1, \phi)$	+1	0	0
$\vec{\pi}_6 = (1, 1+1, \phi, \phi)$	+1	2	2
$\vec{\pi}_7 = (1, \phi, 1+1, \phi)$	+1	-2	1
$\vec{\pi}_8 = (1, \phi, \phi, 2)$	+1	0	0
	$\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 6$		

Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition.

Thus we have, $N_{\overline{S_1}}(0,3,3) = +1+1-1+1 = 2$, $N_{\overline{S_1}}(1,3,3) = 1+1 = 2$, $N_{\overline{S_1}}(2,3,3) = 1+1 = 2$

$\therefore N_{\overline{S_1}}(0,3,3) = N_{\overline{S_1}}(1,3,3) = N_{\overline{S_1}}(2,3,3) = 2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 6 = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt_1}(3)$. Hence The Result.

Now from above table we get; $\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 6$

$$i.e. \sum_{k=0}^2 N_{\overline{S_1}}(k,3,3) = 6$$

$$\therefore \overline{spt_1}(3) = \sum_{k=0}^2 N_{\overline{S_1}}(k,3,3) = \sum \omega(\vec{\pi}).$$

Now we can define $N_{\overline{S_1}}(k, t, n) = \sum_{m=k(\text{mod } t)} N_{\overline{S_1}}(m, n)$

$$\text{and } \overline{spt_1}(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} N_{\overline{S_1}}(m, n) = \sum_{k=0}^{t-1} N_{\overline{S_1}}(k, t, n).$$

Result 3: $M_{\overline{S_2}}(0,3,4) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(1,3,4) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(2,3,4) = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt_2}(4)$.

Proof: We prove the result with the help of examples. We see the vector partitions from $\overline{S_2}$ of 4 along with their weights and cranks and are given as follows:

Table 6:

$\overline{S_2}$ -vector partition $(\vec{\pi})$ of 4	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $(\vec{\pi})$	mod 3
$\vec{\pi}_1 = (4, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	1	0	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (2+2, \phi, \phi)$	1	1	1
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (2, \phi, 2, \phi)$	1	-1	2
	$\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 3$		

Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition. Thus we have,

$$M_{\overline{S_2}}(0,3,4) = 1, \quad M_{\overline{S_2}}(1,3,4) = 1,$$

$$M_{\overline{S_2}}(2,3,4) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(-1,3,4) = 1$$

$$\therefore M_{\overline{S_2}}(0,3,4) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(1,3,4)$$

$$= M_{\overline{S_2}}(2,3,4) = 1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 3 = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt_2}(3) \text{ . Hence The Result.}$$

Now from above table we get; $\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 3$, i.e., $\sum_{k=0}^2 M_{\overline{S_2}}(k,3,4) = 3$.

$$\therefore \overline{spt_2}(4) = \sum_{k=0}^2 M_{\overline{S_2}}(k,3,4) = \sum \omega(\vec{\pi}).$$

Now we can define;

$$M_{\overline{S_2}}(k, t, n) = \sum_{m=k(\text{mod } t)} M_{\overline{S_2}}(m, n)$$

$$\text{and } \overline{spt_2}(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\overline{S_2}}(m, n) = \sum_{k=0}^{t-1} M_{\overline{S_2}}(k, t, n).$$

Theorem 1: The number of vector partitions of n in $\overline{S}$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is non-negative. i.e. $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n) \geq 0$.

Proof: The generating function for $M_{\overline{S}}(m, n)$ is given by $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_m M_{\overline{S}}(m, n) z^m x^n$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [\text{since } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} \\
 &= (x^2; x)_{\infty} (-x^2; x)_{\infty} + (x^3; x)_{\infty} (-x^3; x)_{\infty} + (x^4; x)_{\infty} (-x^4; x)_{\infty} + \dots \\
 &= (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots(1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots + (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots\dots(1+x^3)(1+x^4)\dots \\
 &= (1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots + (1-x^6)(1-x^8) + \dots\dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}] \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 & [\text{since } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{(x^4; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x^2)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^6; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x^2)_{\infty}} + \dots \\
 &= \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots}{(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x^2)} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^3)(1-x^5)\dots} + \frac{1}{(1-x^4)} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^5)(1-x^7)\dots} + \dots \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-x^{2n}} \cdot \frac{1}{(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}}] \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^n \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^n)^k}{(zx^{n+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 & [\text{since } = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n \cdot (x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^n \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^n)^k}{(zx^{n+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k}] \text{ (by [3])}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that the co-efficient of any power x in right hand side is non-negative so the

co-efficient $M_{\vec{S}}(m, n)$ of $z^m x^n$ is non-negative, i.e. $M_{\vec{S}}(m, n) \geq 0$. Hence the Theorem.

Numerical example 1: The vector partitions from $\vec{S}$ of 4 along with their weights and cranks are given as follows:

Table 7:

$\vec{S}$ -vector partition $\vec{\pi}$ of 4	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $c(\vec{\pi})$

$\vec{\pi}_1 = (4, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	+ 1	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (3+1, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	-1	0
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (1,3, \phi, \phi)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_4 = (1, \phi, 3, \phi)$	+1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_5 = (1, \phi, \phi, 3)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_6 = (2, 2, \phi, \phi)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_7 = (2, \phi, 2, \phi)$	+1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_8 = (1+2, 1, \phi, \phi)$	-1	1
$\vec{\pi}_9 = (1+ 2, \phi, 1, \phi)$	-1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_{10} = (1, 1, 2, \phi)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_{11} = (1, 2, 1, \phi)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_{12} = (1, 1, \phi, 2)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_{13} = (1, \phi, 1, 2)$	+1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_{14} = (1, 1+ 2, \phi, \phi)$	+1	2
$\vec{\pi}_{15} = (1, \phi, 1+ 2, \phi)$	+1	-2
$\vec{\pi}_{16} = (1, 1+ 1+ 1, \phi, \phi)$	+1	3
$\vec{\pi}_{17} = (1, \phi, 1+ 1+ 1, \phi)$	+1	-3
$\vec{\pi}_{18} = (1, 1+ 1, 1, \phi)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_{19} = (1, 1, 1+ 1, \phi)$	+1	-1

	$\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 13$	
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Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition. Thus we have;

$$M_{\vec{S}}(0,4) = 3, M_{\vec{S}}(1,4) = 3, M_{\vec{S}}(-1,4) = 3, M_{\vec{S}}(2,4) = 1, M_{\vec{S}}(-2,4) = 1, M_{\vec{S}}(3,4) = 1, \text{ and } M_{\vec{S}}(-3,4) = 1,$$

$$\therefore \sum_m M_{\vec{S}}(m,4) = 13, \text{ i.e. every term is non-negative.}$$

$$\therefore M_{\vec{S}}(m,4) \geq 0. \text{ But we have already found that } \sum_m M_{\vec{S}}(m,3) = 6,$$

i.e., every term is non-negative. $\therefore M_{\vec{S}}(m,3) \geq 0.$

So we can conclude that; $M_{\vec{S}}(m, n) \geq 0.$

Theorem 2: The number of vector partitions of n in $\vec{S}_1$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is non-negative. i.e. $N_{\vec{S}_1}(m, n) \geq 0.$

Proof: The generating function for $N_{\vec{S}_1}(m, n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_m N_{\vec{S}_1}(m, n) z^m x^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot (x^{4n+4}; x^2)_{\infty}$$

[since $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}$

$$= (x^2; x)_{\infty} (-x^2; x)_{\infty} + (x^4; x)_{\infty} (-x^4; x)_{\infty} + \dots$$

$$= (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots(1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots + (1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots(1+x^4)(1+x^5)\dots + \dots$$

$$= (1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots + (1-x^8)(1-x^{10})\dots + (1-x^{12})\dots + \dots$$

$$= (x^4; x^2)_{\infty} + (x^8; x^2)_{\infty} + (x^{12}; x^2)_{\infty} + \dots = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (x^{4n+4}; x^2)_{\infty}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{4n+4}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(x^{4n+5}; x^2)_{\infty}}$$

[since $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n+4}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}} = \frac{(x^4; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^8; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^8; x)_{\infty}} + \dots$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^4)(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots} + \frac{(1-x^8)(1-x^{10})\dots}{(1-x^8)(1-x^9)\dots} + \dots \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x^5)(1-x^7)\dots} + \frac{1}{(1-x^9)(1-x^{11})\dots} + \dots \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(x^{4n+5}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^{2n+1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^{2n+1})^k}{(zx^{2n+1+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k} \cdot \frac{1}{(x^{4n+5}; x^2)_{\infty}}
 \end{aligned}$$

[since $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^{2n+1} \frac{(x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{4n+4}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^{2n+1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^{2n+1})^k}{(zx^{2n+1+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k}$]. (by [3])

We see that the co-efficient of any power x in the right hand side is non-negative so the co-efficient $N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n)$ of $z^m x^n$ is non-negative. i.e. $N_{\bar{S}_1}(m, n) \geq 0$. Hence the Theorem.

Numerical Example 2:

The vector partitions from $\bar{S}_1$ of 3 along with their weights and cranks are given as follows:

Table 8:

$\bar{S}_1$ -vector partition $\vec{\pi}$ of 3	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $c(\vec{\pi})$
$\vec{\pi}_1 = (1, \phi, \phi, 2)$	+ 1	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (1, 1, 1, \phi)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (1+2, \phi, \phi)$	-1	0
$\vec{\pi}_4 = (3, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	+1	0
$\vec{\pi}_5 = (1, \phi, 1+1, \phi)$	+1	-2
$\vec{\pi}_6 = (1, 2, \phi, \phi)$	+1	1
$\vec{\pi}_7 = (1, \phi, 2, \phi)$	+1	-1
$\vec{\pi}_8 = (1, 1+1, \phi, \phi)$	+1	2

	$\sum \omega = 6$	
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Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition. Thus we have

$$N_{\bar{S}_1}(0,3) = 2, \quad N_{\bar{S}_1}(-1,3) = 1, \quad N_{\bar{S}_1}(1,3) = 1, \quad N_{\bar{S}_1}(-2,3) = 1, \quad N_{\bar{S}_1}(2,3) = 1,$$

$\therefore$ every term is non-negative and $N_{\bar{S}_1}(m,3) = 6$, i.e. $N_{\bar{S}_1}(m,n) \geq 0$.

We can conclude that $N_{\bar{S}_1}(m,n) \geq 0$.

Theorem 3: The number of vector partitions of n in $\bar{S}_2$ with crank m counted according to the weight ω is non-negative, i.e., $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m,n) \geq 0$.

Proof: The generating function for $M_{\bar{S}_2}(m,n)$ is given by; $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} M_{\bar{S}_2}(m,n) z^m x^n$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot (x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}.$$

[Since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} = (x^3; x)_{\infty} (-x^3; x)_{\infty} + (x^5; x)_{\infty} (-x^5; x)_{\infty} + \dots$

$$= (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots(1+x^3)(1+x^4)\dots + (1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots(1+x^5)\dots + \dots$$

$$= (1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots + (1-x^{10})(1-x^{12})\dots + (1-x^{14})\dots + \dots$$

$$= (x^6; x^2)_{\infty} + (x^{10}; x^2)_{\infty} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{4n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{4n}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{4n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{4n})(x^{4n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}}$$

[Since, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{4n}; x)_{\infty}} = \frac{(x^6; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^{10}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^8; x)_{\infty}} + \dots = \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots}{(1-x^4)(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots} +$

$$\frac{(1-x^{10})(1-x^{12})\dots}{(1-x^8)(1-x^9)(1-x^{10})(1-x^{11})\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1-x^4)(1-x^5)(1-x^7)\dots} + \frac{1}{(1-x^8)(1-x^9)(1-x^{11})\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-x^{4n}} \cdot \frac{1}{(x^{4n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^{2n} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^{2n})^k}{(zx^{2n+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{4n})(x^{4n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}}$$

[Since, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (x^{4n}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^{2n} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^{-1}x^{2n})^k}{(zx^{2n+k}; x)_{\infty} (x)_k}$. (by [3])

We see that the coefficient of any power x in the right hand side is non-negative so the coefficient $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n)$ of $z^m x^n$ is non-negative, i.e., $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n) \geq 0$. Hence the Theorem.

Numerical Example 3:

The vector partitions from $\overline{S}_2$ of 5 along with their weights and cranks are given as follows:

Table 9:

$\overline{S}_2$ -vector partition $\vec{\pi}$ of 5	Weight $\omega(\vec{\pi})$	Crank $c(\vec{\pi})$
$\vec{\pi}_1 = (3+2, \phi, \phi, \phi)$	-1	0
$\vec{\pi}_2 = (2, \phi, \phi, 3)$	1	0
$\vec{\pi}_3 = (2, 3, \phi, \phi)$	1	1
$\vec{\pi}_4 = (2, \phi, 3, \phi)$	1	-1
	$\sum \omega(\vec{\pi}) = 2$	

Here we have used ϕ to indicate the empty partition. Thus we have;

$$M_{\overline{S}_2}(0,5) = 1 - 1 = 0, M_{\overline{S}_2}(1,5) = 1, \text{ and } M_{\overline{S}_2}(-1,5) = 1, \text{ i.e., } \sum_m M_{\overline{S}_2}(m,5) = 2,$$

i.e., every term is non-negative, i.e., $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n) \geq 0$.

So we can conclude that, $M_{\overline{S}_2}(m, n) \geq 0$.

Corollary 4: $\overline{S}(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n)x^n.$

Proof: We get $\overline{S}(z, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^n; x)_{\infty} (z^{-1}x^n; x)_{\infty}}$ ([2]).

If $z = 1$, then we get; $\overline{S}(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty} (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^n; x)_{\infty} (x^n; x)_{\infty}}$

$$= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty} (x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(x; x)_{\infty}^2} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty} (x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}^2} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty} (1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2\dots} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty} (1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)^2\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n (-x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^n)^2 (x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n)x^n,$$

i.e; $\bar{S}(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n)x^n$. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 5: $\bar{S}_1(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_1(n)x^n$

Proof: we get $\bar{S}_1(z, x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}(-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}(x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}(z^{-1}x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}$ ([2]).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } z = 1, \text{ then we get; } \bar{S}_1(1, x) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}(-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}(x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \\ &= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}(x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(x; x)_{\infty}(x; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty}(x^4; x)_{\infty}}{(x^3; x)_{\infty}(x^3; x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\ &= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2\dots} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty}(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots}{(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)^2\dots} + \dots \\ &= \frac{x(-x^2; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^3(-x^4; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^3)^2(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \dots \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}(-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2(x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}} \end{aligned}$$

i.e; $\bar{S}_1(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_1(n)x^n$. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 6: $\bar{S}_2(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_2(n)x^n$.

Proof: We get; $\bar{S}_2(z, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}(-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(zx^{2n}; x)_{\infty}(z^{-1}x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}$ [2].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } z = 1, \text{ then we get; } \bar{S}_2(1, x) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}(-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} \\ &= \frac{x^2(x^3; x)_{\infty}(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}^2} + \frac{x^4(-x^5; x)_{\infty}(x^5; x)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x)_{\infty}^2} + \dots \\ &= \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)^2\dots} + \frac{x^4(-x^5; x)_{\infty}(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^4)^2(1-x^5)^2\dots} + \dots \\ &= \frac{x^2(-x^3; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^4(-x^5; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^4)^2(1-x^5)\dots} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}(-x^{2n+1};x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n})^2(x^{2n+1};x)_{\infty}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_2(n) x^n.$$

i.e., $\overline{S}_2(1, x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_2(n) x^n$. Hence The Corollary.

Theorem 4: $\overline{spt}(n) = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in SP \\ |\lambda| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} 1$.

Proof: First we define the $\overline{spt}$ crankin terms of partition pairs.

$\overline{SP} = \{ \overline{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in P \times P : 1 < s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2) \text{ and all parts of } \lambda_2 \text{ that are } \geq 2s(\lambda_1) + 1 \text{ are odd} \}$.

The generating function for $\overline{spt}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}(n) x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n(-x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}} (-x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{2n+2};x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}}$$

[since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-x^{n+1};x)_{\infty} = (-x^2;x)_{\infty} + (-x^3;x)_{\infty} + \dots$

$$= (1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots + (1+x^3)(1+x^4)\dots + (1+x^4)\dots$$

$$= \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{(x^4;x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^2;x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^6;x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^3;x)_{\infty}} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{2n+2};x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(x^n;x)_{\infty}(1-x^n)} \cdot \frac{(x^{2n+2};x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}}$$

[since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1-x^n)^2(x^{n+1};x)_{\infty}} = \frac{x}{(1-x)^2(x^2;x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^2}{(1-x^2)^2(x^3;x)_{\infty}} + \dots$

$$= \frac{x}{(1-x)^2(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} + \frac{x^2}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{x}{(1-x)(x;x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^2}{(1-x^2)(x^2;x)_{\infty}} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1-x^n)(x^n;x)_{\infty}}]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^n)} \cdot \frac{(x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^n)} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{n+1}) \dots (1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 &\quad [\text{since } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{2n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \frac{(x^4; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^6; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^3; x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\
 &\quad = \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^4)\dots}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \dots \\
 &\quad = \frac{1}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)(1-x^7)\dots} + \frac{1}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \dots \\
 &\quad = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{n+1}) \dots (1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}}] \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(x^n; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^n)(1-x^{n+1}) \dots (1-x^{2n})(x^{2n+1}; x^2)_{\infty}} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\lambda_1 \in P} x^{|\lambda_1|} \cdot \sum_{\lambda_2 \in P} x^{|\lambda_2|} \\
 &\quad s(\lambda_1) = n \qquad s(\lambda_2) \geq n \\
 &\quad \text{all parts in } \lambda_2 \geq 2n+1 \text{ are odd} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in \overline{SP} \\ |\bar{\lambda}| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} x^{|\bar{\lambda}|} .
 \end{aligned}$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$\overline{spt}(n) = \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in \overline{SP} \\ |\bar{\lambda}| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} 1 . \text{ Hence The Theorem.}$$

Numerical example 4:

The overpartitions of 3 with smallest parts not overlined are $3, 2+1, \bar{2}+1, 1+1+1$

Consequently, the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of 3 with smallest part not overlined is given by $\overset{\cdot}{3}, \overset{\cdot}{2}+1, \overset{\cdot}{\bar{2}}+1, \overset{\cdot}{1}+\overset{\cdot}{1}+\overset{\cdot}{1}$ so that $\overline{spt}(3) = 6$

i.e. there are 6 $\overline{SP}$ -partition pairs of 3 like $(3, \phi), (2+1, \phi), (1+1+1, \phi), (1, 1, 1), (1, 1+1)$ and $(1, 2)$.

Theorem 5: $\overline{spt}_1(n) = \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in SP_1 \\ |\bar{\lambda}| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} 1$

Proof: First we define the *sptcrank* in terms of partition pairs.

$$\overline{SP} = \{ \bar{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in P \times P : 0 < s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2) \text{ and all parts of } \lambda_2 \text{ that are } \geq 2s(\lambda_1) + 1 \text{ are odd} \}.$$

The generating function for $\overline{spt}_1(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_1(n) x^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2 (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n+1}}{(1-x^{2n+1})^2 (x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}$$

[since $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-x^{2n+2}; x)_{\infty} = (-x^2; x)_{\infty} + (-x^4; x)_{\infty} + (-x^6; x)_{\infty} + ..$

$$= (1+x^2)(1+x^3)(1+x^4)..... + (1+x^4)(1+x^5).... + (1+x^6).... + ...$$

$$= \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^6)..\ (1-x^8)(1-x^{10})... + (1-x^{12})..}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)...\ (1-x^4)(1-x^5)..\ (1-x^6)..\ } + ..$$

$$= \frac{(x^4; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^2; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^8; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^4; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^{12}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^6; x)_{\infty}} + .. = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}}]$$

$$= \frac{x}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)...\ (1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)....}$$

$$+ \frac{x^2}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)...\ (1-x^3)(1-x^4)...\ (1-x^7)(1-x^9)....}$$

$$+ \frac{x^5}{(1-x^5)(1-x^6)...\ (1-x^5)(1-x^6)...\ (1-x^{11})(1-x^{13})....} + ...$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n-1}}{(x^{2n-1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n-1})(1-x^{2n})...\ (1-x^{4n-2})(x^{4n-1}; x^2)_{\infty}}$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\lambda_1 \in P} x^{|\lambda_1|} \sum_{\lambda_2 \in P} x^{|\lambda_2|}$$

$$s(\lambda_1) = n \quad s(\lambda_2) \geq n$$

all parts in $\lambda_2 \geq 2n + 1$ are odd

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in \overline{SP}_1 \\ |\bar{\lambda}| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} x^{|\bar{\lambda}|} .$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$\overline{spt}_1(n) = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in SP_1 \\ |\lambda| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} 1 \quad . \quad \text{Hence The Theorem.}$$

Numerical Example 5:

The overpartitions of 4 with smallest part not overlined and odd are $3+1, \overline{3}+1, 2+1+1, \overline{2}+1+1$ and $1+1+1+1$.

Consequently, the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of 4 with smallest part not overlined and odd is given by; $3+1, \overline{3}+1, 2+1+1, \overline{2}+1+1, 1+1+1+1$ so that $\overline{spt}_1(4) = 10$ i.e., there are 10 $\overline{SP}_1$ -partition pairs of 4 like-

$(3+1, \phi), (1,3), (2+1+1, \phi), (2+1,1), (1,1+2), (1+1,2), (1+1+1+1, \phi), (1+1+1,1), (1+1,1+1)$ and $(1, 1+1+1)$.

Theorem 6: $\overline{spt}_2(n) = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \overline{SP}_2 \\ |\lambda| = |\lambda_1| + |\lambda_2| = n}} 1$

Proof: First we define the $\overline{sptcrank}$ in terms of partition pairs,

$$\overline{SP} = \{ \overline{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in P \times P : 0 < s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2) \text{ and all parts of } \lambda_2 \text{ that are } \geq 2s(\lambda_1) + 1 \text{ are odd} \}.$$

Let $\overline{SP}_2$ be the set of $\overline{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP}$ with $s(\lambda_1)$ even. The generating function for $\overline{spt}_2(n)$ is given

$$\begin{aligned} \text{by; } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{spt}_2(n) x^n &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}{(1-x^{2n})^2 (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(1-x^{2n})^2 (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(1-x^{2n})^2 (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \end{aligned}$$

[Since, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty} = (-x^3; x)_{\infty} + (-x^5; x)_{\infty} + \dots$

$$= (1+x^3)(1+x^4) \dots + (1+x^5)(1+x^6) \dots + (1+x^7)(1+x^8) \dots + \dots$$

$$= \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^8) \dots}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4) \dots} + \frac{(1-x^{10})(1-x^{12}) \dots}{(1-x^5)(1-x^6) \dots} + \frac{(1-x^{14}) \dots}{(1-x^7) \dots} + \dots$$

$$= \frac{(x^6; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^3; x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^{10}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^5; x)_{\infty}} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(1-x^{2n})^2 (x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(x^{2n}; x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})} \cdot \frac{(x^{4n+2}; x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1}; x)_{\infty}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [\text{Since, } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(1-x^{2n})^2(x^{2n+1};x)_{\infty}} = \frac{x^2}{(1-x^2)^2(x^3;x)_{\infty}} + \frac{x^4}{(1-x^4)^2(x^5;x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{x^2}{(1-x^2)^2(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \frac{x^4}{(1-x^4)^2(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(x^{2n};x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})}] \\
 & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{(x^{2n};x)_{\infty}} \cdot \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n})(1-x^{2n+1})\dots(1-x^{4n})(x^{4n+1};x^2)_{\infty}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [\text{Since, } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(x^{4n+2};x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^{2n+1};x)_{\infty}} = \frac{(x^6;x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^3;x)_{\infty}} + \frac{(x^{10};x^2)_{\infty}}{(x^5;x)_{\infty}} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)\dots} + \frac{(1-x^{10})(1-x^{12})\dots}{(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots(1-x^{10})(1-x^{11})\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \frac{1}{(1-x^3)(1-x^4)(1-x^5)\dots} + \frac{1}{(1-x^5)(1-x^6)\dots(1-x^9)(1-x^{11})\dots} + \dots \\
 & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{2n+1})\dots(1-x^{4n})(x^{4n+1};x^2)_{\infty}}] \\
 & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{\lambda_1 \in P \\ s(\lambda_1)=n}} x^{|\lambda_1|} \sum_{\substack{\lambda_2 \in P \\ s(\lambda_2) \geq n}} x^{|\lambda_2|}
 \end{aligned}$$

all parts in $\lambda_2 \geq 2n + 1$ are odd

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in SP_2 \\ |\bar{\lambda}|=|\lambda_1|+|\lambda_2|=n}} x^{|\bar{\lambda}|} .$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$\overline{spt}_2(n) = \sum_{\substack{\bar{\lambda} \in SP_2 \\ |\bar{\lambda}|=|\lambda_1|+|\lambda_2|=n}} 1 \quad . \text{ Hence The Theorem.}$$

Numerical Example 6:

The overpartitions of 6 with smallest parts not overlined and even are 6, $4+2$, $\overline{4}+2$, and $2+2+2$. Consequently, the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of 6 with smallest part not overlined and even is given by;

$$\overset{\cdot}{6} \quad \overset{\cdot}{4}+\overset{\cdot}{2}, \quad \overline{\overset{\cdot}{4}}+\overset{\cdot}{2}, \quad \overset{\cdot}{2}+\overset{\cdot}{2}+\overset{\cdot}{2},$$

so that $\overline{spt}_2(6) = 6$ i.e., there are 6 $\overline{SP}_2$ -partition pairs of 6 like:

$(6, \phi), (4 + 2, \phi), (2, 4), (2 + 2 + 2, \phi), (2 + 2, 2)$ and $(2, 2 + 2)$.

Result 4: $M_{\overline{S}}(0,3,3) = M_{\overline{S}}(1,3,3) = M_{\overline{S}}(2,3,3) = \frac{\overline{spt}(3)}{3}$.

Proof: First we define a $\overline{crank}$ of partitions pairs $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP}$.

For $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP}$ we define;

$k(\vec{\lambda}) = \#$ of pairs j in λ_2 such that $s(\lambda_1) \leq j \leq 2s(\lambda_1) - 1, s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2)$,
and also define

$$\overline{crank}(\vec{\lambda}) = \begin{cases} (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1 \geq s(\lambda_1) + k) - k; & \text{if } k > 0 \\ (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1) - 1; & \text{if } k = 0 \end{cases}$$

where $k = k(\vec{\lambda})$.

Table 10:

$\overline{SP}$ -partition pair $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$	K	$\overline{crank}$	(mod3)
$(3, \phi)$	0	0	0
$(2 + 1, \phi)$	0	1	1
$(1 + 1 + 1, \phi)$	0	2	2
$(1 + 1, 1)$	1	-1	2
$(1, 1 + 1)$	2	-2	1
$(1, 2)$	0	0	0

From the table we get;

$$M_{\overline{S}}(0,3,3) = M_{\overline{S}}(1,3,3) = M_{\overline{S}}(2,3,3) = 2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 6 = \frac{1}{3} \overline{spt}(3). \text{ Hence The Result.}$$

Result 5: $N_{\overline{S}_1}(0,5,5) = N_{\overline{S}_1}(1,5,5) = N_{\overline{S}_1}(2,5,5) = N_{\overline{S}_1}(3,5,5) = N_{\overline{S}_1}(4,5,5) = 4 = \frac{1}{5} \overline{spt}_1(5)$

Proof: We prove the result with the help of an example.

We can define a $\overline{crank}$ of partition pairs $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP}_1$. For $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP}_1$ we define

$k(\vec{\lambda}) = \#$ of parts j in λ_2 such that $s(\lambda_1) \leq j \leq 2s(\lambda_1) - 1, s(\lambda_1) \leq s(\lambda_2)$

and also define;

$$\overline{crank}(\vec{\lambda}) = \begin{cases} (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1 \geq s(\lambda_1) + k) - k; & \text{if } k > 0 \\ (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1) - 1; & \text{if } k = 0 \end{cases}$$

where $k = k(\vec{\lambda})$.

The number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of 5 with smallest part not overlined and odd is given by;

$$\dot{5}, 4+\dot{1}, \bar{4}+\dot{1}, 3+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \bar{3}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, 2+2+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+2+\dot{1}, 2+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \bar{2}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}, \dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1}+\dot{1},$$

so that $\overline{spt}_1(5) = 20$. There are 20 $\overline{SP}_1$ - partition pairs of 5.

Table 11:

$\overline{SP}_1$ -partition pair of 5	K	$\overline{crank}$	(mod 5)
(1, 2+2)	0	0	0
(2+1+1,1)	1	0	0
(3+1,1)	1	0	0
(5, ϕ)	0	0	0
(1, 1+1+1+1)	4	-4	1
(1+1, 3)	0	1	1
(2+1,2)	0	1	1
(4+1, ϕ)	0	1	1
(1+1, 1+1+1)	3	-3	2
(1+1+1, 2)	0	2	2
(2+2+1, ϕ)	0	2	2
(3+1+1, ϕ)	0	2	2
(1, 2+1+1)	2	-2	3
(1+1+1, 1+1)	2	-2	3
(2+1, 1+1)	2	-2	3
(2+1+1+1, ϕ)	0	3	3
(1, 3+1)	1	-1	4
(1+1, 2+1)	1	-1	4
(1+1+1+1, 1)	1	-1	4
(1+1+1+1+1, ϕ)	0	4	4

From the table we get; $N_{\overline{S_1}}(0,5,5) = N_{\overline{S_1}}(1,5,5) = N_{\overline{S_1}}(2,5,5) = N_{\overline{S_1}}(3,5,5) =$

$$N_{\overline{S_1}}(4,5,5) = 4 = \frac{1}{5} \overline{spt_1}(5). \text{ Hence The Result.}$$

Result 6: $M_{\overline{S_2}}(0,5,8) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(1,5,8) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(2,5,8) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(3,5,8) = M_{\overline{S_2}}(4,5,8) = 3 = \frac{1}{5} \overline{spt_2}(8).$

Proof: We prove the result with the help of examples. We can define a $\overline{crank}$ of partition pairs $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP_2}$.

For $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \overline{SP_2}$, we define, $k(\vec{\lambda}) = \#$ of pairs j in λ_2 such that $s(\lambda_1) \leq j \leq 2s(\lambda_1) - 1$, and also

$$\text{define; } \overline{crank}(\vec{\lambda}) = \begin{cases} (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1 \geq s(\lambda_1) + k) - k; \\ \text{if } k > 0 \\ (\# \text{ of parts of } \lambda_1) - 1; \text{ if } k = 0 \end{cases} \text{ where } k = k(\vec{\lambda}).$$

We know that $\overline{spt_2}(8) = 15$. There are 15 $\overline{SP_2}$ -partition pairs of 8.

Table 12:

$\overline{SP_2}$ -partition pair of 8	K	$\overline{crank}$	(mod 5)
(3+2, 3)	1	0	0
(4+2, 2)	1	0	0
(8, ϕ)	0	0	0
(2+2, 4)	0	1	1
(4+4, ϕ)	0	1	1
(6+2, ϕ)	0	1	1
(2, 2+2+2)	3	-3	2
(3+3+2, ϕ)	0	2	2
(4+2+2, ϕ)	0	2	2
(2, 3+3)	2	-2	3
(2+2, 2+2)	2	-2	3
(2+2+2+2, ϕ)	0	3	3
(2, 4+2)	1	-1	4
(4, 4)	1	-1	4
(2+2+2, 2)	1	-1	4

From the table we get; $M_{\overline{s_2}}(0,5,8) = M_{\overline{s_2}}(1,5,8) = M_{\overline{s_2}}(2,5,8) =$

$$M_{\overline{s_2}}(3,5,8) = M_{\overline{s_2}}(4,5,8) = 3 = \frac{1}{5} \overline{spt_2}(8). \text{ Hence The Result.}$$

4. WE WANT TO DESCRIBE THE $\overline{sptcrank}$ OF A MARKED OVERPARTITION [7]:

To define the $\overline{sptcrank}$ of a marked overpartition we first need to define a function $k(m,n)$ for positive integers m and n such that $m \geq n+1$ we write $m = b2^j$, where b is odd and $j \geq 0$. For a given odd integer b and a positive integer n we define $j_0 = j_0(b,n)$ to be the smallest nonnegative integer j_0 such that $b2^{j_0} \geq n+1$.

$$\text{We define; } k(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } b \geq 2n \\ 2^{j-j_0} & \text{if } b2^{j_0} < 2n \\ 0, & \text{if } b2^{j_0} = 2n. \end{cases}$$

It is convenient to define $k(m,n)=0$, if $m=0$.

If $j \geq 1$ then $b2^{j_0} \leq 2n$ so that the function $k(m,n)$ is well-defined. For a partition

$\pi : m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_t$ into distinct parts and $m_1 > m_2 > \dots > m_t \geq n+1$, we define the function

$$k(\pi,n) = \sum_{j=1}^t k(m_j,n) = \sum_{m \in \pi} k(m,n).$$

For a marked overpartitions (π, j) we let π_1 be the partition formed by the non-overlined parts of π , π_2 be the partition (into distinct parts) formed by the overlined parts of π so that $s(\pi_2) > s(\pi_1)$, we define $\bar{k}(\pi, i) = \nu(\pi_1) - j + k(\pi_2, s(\pi_1))$, where $\nu(\pi_1)$ is the number of smallest parts of π_1 . Now we can define;

$$\overline{sptcrank}(\pi, j) = \begin{cases} (\# \text{ of parts of } \pi_1 \geq s(\pi_1) + \bar{k}) - \bar{k}, & \text{if } \bar{k} = \bar{k}(\pi, j) > 0 \\ (\# \text{ of parts of } \pi_1) - 1; & \text{if } \bar{k} = \bar{k}(\pi, j) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 7[9]: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank} \pmod 3$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ into 3 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the corollary with the help of an example. There are 42 marked overpartitions of $3n$ (where $n = 2$) so that $\overline{spt}(6) = 42$.

Table 13:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 6	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod3)
(6,1)	6	ϕ	1	0	0	0	0

$(\bar{5}+1,1)$	1	5	1	0	0	0	0
$(\bar{4}+2,1)$	2	4	1	0	0	0	0
$(4+1+1,1)$	4+1+1	ϕ	2	0	1	0	0
$(\bar{3}+\bar{2}+1,1)$	1	3+ 2	1	0	0	0	0
$(3+1+1+1,2)$	3+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	1	0	0
$(3+1+1+1,3)$	3+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	0	3	0
$(2+2+1+1,2)$	2+2+1+1	ϕ	2	0	0	3	0
$(\bar{2}+2+1+1,2)$	2+1+1	2	2	0	1	0	0
$(2+1+1+1+1,1)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	3	-3	0
$(2+1+1+1+1,3)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	1	0	0
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,1)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	3	-3	0
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,4)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	0	-3	0
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,3)$	1+1+1+1+1 +1	ϕ	6	0	3	-3	0
$(5+1,1)$	5+1	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
$(4+2,1)$	4+2	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{4}+1+1,2)$	1+1	4	2	0	0	1	1
$(3+3,2)$	3+3	ϕ	2	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{3}+2+1,1)$	2+1	3	1	0	0	1	1
$(3+\bar{2}+1,1)$	3+1	2	1	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{3}+1+1+1,1)$	1+1+1	3	3	0	2	-2	1
$(2+2+2,1)$	2+2+2	ϕ	3	0	2	-2	1
$(2+2+1+1,1)$	2+2+1+1	ϕ	2	0	1	1	1
$(2+1+1+1+1,2)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	2	-2	1

$(2+1+1+1+1,4)$	$2+1+1+1+1$	ϕ	4	0	0	4	1
$(\overline{2}+1+1+1+1,2)$	$1+1+1+1$	2	4	0	2	-2	1
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,1)$	$1+1+1+1+1+1$	ϕ	6	0	5	-5	1
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,4)$	$1+1+1+1+1+1$	ϕ	6	0	2	-2	1
$(4+1+1,2)$	$4+1+1$	ϕ	2	0	0	2	2
$(\overline{4}+1+1,1)$	$1+1$	4	2	0	1	-1	2
$(3+3,1)$	$3+3$	ϕ	2	0	1	-1	2
$(3+2+1,1)$	$3+2+1$	ϕ	1	0	0	2	2
$(3+1+1+1,1)$	$3+1+1+1$	ϕ	3	0	2	-1	2
$(\overline{3}+1+1+1,2)$	$1+1+1$	3	3	0	1	-1	2
$(\overline{3}+1+1+1,3)$	$1+1+1$	3	3	0	0	2	2
$(2+2+2,2)$	$2+2+2$	ϕ	3	0	1	-1	2
$(2+2+2,3)$	$2+2+2$	ϕ	3	0	0	2	2
$(\overline{2}+2+1+1,2)$	$2+1+1$	2	2	0	0	2	2
$(\overline{2}+1+1+1+1,3)$	$1+1+1+1$	2	4	0	1	-1	2
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,2)$	$(1+1+1+1+1+1)$	ϕ	6	0	4	-4	2
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,5)$	$(1+1+1+1+1+1)$	ϕ	6	0	1	-1	2
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,6)$	$(1+1+1+1+1+1)$	ϕ	6	0	0	5	2

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank} \pmod{3}$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ into 3 equal classes. Hence the Corollary.

Corollary 8 [9]: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank} \pmod{3}$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ with smallest part not overlined and odd into 3 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the Corollary with the help of example. There are 36 marked overpartitions of $3n$ (when $n = 2$) with the smallest part not overlined and odd so that $\overline{spt}_1(6) = 36$.

Table 13:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 6	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod3)
(5+1,1)	5+1	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
($\bar{5}+1,1$)	1	5	1	0	0	0	0
(4+1+1,1)	4+1+1	ϕ	2	0	1	0	0
(4+1+1,2)	4+1+1	ϕ	2	0	0	2	2
($\bar{4}+1+1,1$)	1+1	4	2	0	1	-1	2
($\bar{4}+1+1,2$)	1+1	4	2	0	0	1	1
(3+3,1)	3+3	ϕ	2	0	1	-1	2
(3+3,2)	3+3	ϕ	2	0	0	1	1
(3+2+1,1)	3+2+1	ϕ	1	0	0	2	2
($\bar{3}+2+1,1$)	2+1	3	1	0	0	1	1
(3+ $\bar{2}+1,1$)	3+1	2	1	0	0	1	1
($\bar{3}+\bar{2}+1,1$)	1	3+2	1	0	0	0	0
(3+1+1+1,1)	3+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	2	-1	2
(3+1+1+1,2)	3+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	1	0	0
(3+1+1+1,3)	3+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	0	3	0
($\bar{3}+1+1+1,1$)	1+1+1	3	3	0	2	-2	1
($\bar{3}+1+1+1,2$)	1+1+1	3	3	0	1	-1	2
($\bar{3}+1+1+1,3$)	1+1+1	3	3	0	0	2	2
(2+2+1+1,1)	2+2+1+1	ϕ	2	0	1	1	1
(2+2+1+1,2)	2+2+1+1	ϕ	2	0	0	3	0
($\bar{2}+2+1+1,1$)	2+1+1	2	2	0	1	0	0

$(\bar{2}+2+1+1,2)$	2+1+1	2	2	0	0	2	2
$(2+1+1+1+1,1)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	3	-3	0
$(2+1+1+1+1,2)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	2	-2	1
$(2+1+1+1+1,3)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	1	0	0
$(2+1+1+1+1,4)$	2+1+1+1+1	ϕ	4	0	0	4	1
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,1)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	3	-3	0
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,2)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	2	-2	1
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,3)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	1	-1	2
$(\bar{2}+1+1+1+1,4)$	1+1+1+1	2	4	0	0	3	0
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,1)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	5	-5	1
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,2)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	4	-4	2
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,3)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	3	-3	0
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,4)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	2	-2	1
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,5)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	1	-1	2
$(1+1+1+1+1+1,6)$	1+1+1+1+1+1	ϕ	6	0	0	5	2

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank} \pmod 3$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ with smallest part not overlined and odd into 3 equal classes. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 9: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank} \pmod 5$ divides the marked overpartitions of $5n$ with smallest part not overlined and odd into 5 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the corollary with the help of example. There are 260 marked overpartitions of $5n$ (when $n = 2$) with smallest part not overlined and odd so that $\overline{spt}_1(10) = 260$.

Table 14:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 10	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	$\pmod 5$
$(\bar{9}+1,1)$	1	9	1	0	0	0	0
$(8+1+1,1)$	8+1+1	ϕ	2	0	1	0	0

$(\bar{7} + 3, 1)$	3	7	1	0	0	0	0
$(\bar{7} + \bar{2} + 1, 1)$	1	7+2	1	0	0	0	0
$(7 + 1 + 1 + 1, 2)$	7+1+1+1	ϕ	3	0	1	0	0
... ..							
There are 52 marked overpartitions with $\overline{sptcrank}$ congruent 0 (mod 5)							

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 10	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 5)
$(9 + 1, 1)$	9+1	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{8} + 1 + 1, 2)$	1+1	8	2	0	0	1	1
$(7 + 3, 1)$	7+3	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{7} + 2 + 1, 1)$	2+1	7	1	0	0	1	1
$(7 + \bar{2} + 1, 1)$	7+1	2	1	0	0	1	1
... ..							
There are 52 marked overpartitions with $\overline{sptcrank}$ congruent 1 (mod 5)							

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 10	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 5)
$(8+1+1, 2)$	8+1+1	ϕ	2	0	0	2	2
$(7+2+1, 1)$	7+2+1	7	1	0	0	2	2
$(\bar{7} + 1 + 1 + 1, 3)$	1+1+1	7	3	0	0	2	2
$(6+3+1, 1)$	6+3+1	ϕ	1	0	0	2	2
$(\bar{6} + 2 + 1 + 1, 2)$	2+1+1	6	2	0	0	2	2
... ..							
There are 52 marked overpartitions with $\overline{sptcrank}$ congruent 2 (mod 5)							

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 10	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 5)
$(7+1+1+1, 3)$	$7+1+1+1$	ϕ	3	0	0	3	3
$(\bar{7}+1+1+1,1)$	$1+1+1$	7	3	0	2	-2	3
$(6+2+1+1,2)$	$6+2+1+1$	ϕ	2	0	0	3	3
$(\bar{6}+1+1+1+1,2)$	$1+1+1+1$	6	4	0	2	-2	3
$(\bar{6}+1+1+1+1,4)$	$1+1+1+1$	6	4	0	0	3	3
... ..							
There are 52 marked overpartitions with $\overline{sptcrank}$ congruent 3 (mod 5)							

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 10	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 5)
$(\bar{8}+1+1,1)$	$1+1$	8	2	0	1	-1	4
$(7+1+1+1,1)$	$7+1+1+1$	ϕ	3	0	2	-1	4
$(\bar{7}+1+1+1,2)$	$1+1+1$	7	3	0	1	-1	4
$(\bar{6}+\bar{2}+1+1,1)$	$1+1$	$6+2$	2	0	1	-1	4
$(6+1+1+1+1,1)$	$6+1+1+1+1$	ϕ	3	0	2	-1	4
... ..							
There are 52 marked overpartitions with $\overline{sptcrank}$ congruent 4 (mod 5)							

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 5)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $5n$ with smallest part not overlined and odd into 5 equal classes. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 10 [9]: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 3)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ with the smallest part not overlined and even into 3 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the Corollary with the help of an example. There are 6 marked overpartitions of $3n$ (when $n = 2$) with the smallest part not overlined and even so that, $\overline{spt_2}(6) = 6$.

Table 15:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 6	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 3)
(6, 1)	6	ϕ	1	0	0	0	0
(4+2, 1)	4+2	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
($\bar{4}$ +2, 1)	2	4	1	0	0	0	0
(2+2+2, 1)	2+2+2	ϕ	3	0	2	-2	1
(2+2+2, 2)	2+2+2	ϕ	3	0	1	-1	2
(2+2+2, 3)	2+2+2	ϕ	3	0	0	2	2

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 3)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n$ (when $n = 2$) with smallest part not overlined and even into 3 equal classes. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 11: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 3)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n+1$ with smallest part not overlined and even into 3 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the Corollary with the help of an example. There are 6 marked overpartitions of $3n+1$ (when $n = 2$) with the smallest part not overlined and even, so that $\overline{spt}_2(7) = 6$.

Table 16:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 7	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 3)
(5+2, 1)	5+2	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
($\bar{5}$ +2, 1)	2	5	1	0	0	0	0
(3+2+2, 1)	3+2+2	ϕ	2	0	1	0	0
(3+2+2, 2)	3+2+2	ϕ	2	0	0	2	2
($\bar{3}$ +2+2, 1)	2+2	3	2	1	2	-2	1
($\bar{3}$ +2+2, 2)	2+2	3	2	1	1	-1	2

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 3)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $3n+1$ with smallest part not overlined and even. Hence The Corollary.

Corollary 12: The residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 5)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $5n+3$ with smallest part not overlined and even into 5 equal classes.

Proof: We prove the Corollary with the help of example. There are 15 marked overpartitions of $5n + 3$ (when $n = 1$) with the smallest part not overlined and even so that $\overline{spt}_2(8) = 15$.

Table 17:

Marked overpartition (π, j) of 8	π_1	π_2	$\nu(\pi_1)$	$k((\pi_2, s(\pi_1)))$	$\bar{k}$	$\overline{sptcrank}$	(mod 5)
$(\bar{6} + 2, 1)$	2	6	1	2	2	-2	3
$(\bar{4} + 2 + 2, 1)$	2+2	4	2	0	1	-1	4
$(\bar{4} + 2 + 2, 2)$	2+2	4	2	0	0	1	1
$(\bar{3} + 3 + 2, 1)$	3+2	3	1	1	1	0	0
$(2+2+2+2, 1)$	2+2+2+2	ϕ	4	0	3	-3	2
$(2+2+2+2, 2)$	2+2+2+2	ϕ	4	0	2	-2	3
$(2+2+2+2, 3)$	2+2+2+2	ϕ	4	0	1	-1	4
$(2+2+2+2, 4)$	2+2+2+2	ϕ	4	0	0	3	3
$(3+3+2, 1)$	3+3+2	ϕ	1	0	0	2	2
$(4+2+2, 1)$	4+2+2	ϕ	1	0	1	0	0
$(4+2+2, 2)$	4+2+2	ϕ	2	0	0	2	2
$(6+2, 1)$	6+2	ϕ	1	0	0	1	1
$(4+4, 1)$	4+4	ϕ	2	0	1	-1	4
$(4+4, 2)$	4+4	ϕ	2	0	0	1	1
$(8, 1)$	8	ϕ	1	0	0	0	0

We see that the residue of the $\overline{sptcrank}(\text{mod } 5)$ divides the marked overpartitions of $5n + 3$ with the smallest part not overlined and even into 5 equal classes. Hence The corollary.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study we have found the number of smallest parts in the overpartitions of n with smallest part not overlined, not overlined and odd, not overlined and even for $n=1,2,3,4,\dots$ respectively. We have shown the relations $\overline{spt}(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $\overline{spt}_1(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ for $n \geq 0$, $\overline{spt}_1(n) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ if n is an odd square, $\overline{spt}_1(5n) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$, $\overline{spt}_2(3n) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $\overline{spt}_2(3n + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $\overline{spt}_2(5n + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ with the help of induction method and have shown the some results with the help of vector partitions along with their weights and cranks . We have verified the Theorems for certain values of n and have established the some Corollaries with the help of marked overpartitions.

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] G.E. Andrews, F. Dyson, and R. Rhoades. On the distribution of the spt-crank. *Mathematics*, 1(3), 76–88, 2013.
- [2] G.E. Andrews, F.G. Garvan, and J. Liang. Combinatorial interpretations of congruences for the spt-function. *Ramanujan J.*29(1-3):321–338, 2012.
- [3] A. Berkovich and F.G. Garvan. K.Saito's conjecture for nonnegative eta products and analogous results for other infinite products. *J. Number Theory*, 128(6):1731–1748, 2008.
- [4] K. Bringmann, J. Lovejoy, and R. Osburn. Rank and crank moments for overpartitions *J. Number Theory*, 129(7):1758–1772, 2009.
- [5] K. Bringmann, J. Lovejoy, and R. Osburn. Automorphic properties of generating functions for generalized rank moments and Durfee symbols. *Int. Math. Res. Not. IMRN*, (2):238–260, 2010.
- [6] B.C. Berndt, *Ramanujan's notebooks. Part III*. Springer-Verlag, New York, 1991.
- [7] W.Y.C. Chen, K.Q. Ji, and W.J.T. Zang. The spt-crank for ordinary Partitions. *ArXiv e-prints*, Aug. 2013.
- [8] F.G. Garvan and Chris Jennings-Shaffer, The spt-crank for overpartitions arXiv:1311.3680v2[Math.NT],23 Mar 2014.
- [9] J. Lovejoy and R. Osburn. M_2 -rank differences for partitions without repeated odd parts. *J. Theor. Nombres Bordeaux*, 21(2):313-334, 2009.
- [10] Chris Jenning-Shaffer, Another proof of two modulo 3 congruences and another spt crank for the number of smallest parts in overpartitions with even smallest part, arXiv:1406.5458v1 [Math.NT] 20 Jun 2014.